

D1.2 BridgeGap Data Hub

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Disclaimer

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Executive summary

This report outlines the efforts of the BridgeGap Data Hub team, comprised of members of the Transparency International Secretariat, LUISS University, the Romanian Academic Society (SAR) and YouControl, over the past ten months to develop a cutting-edge platform for data visualisation and sharing, aligned with BridgeGap's mission to advance understanding of corruption dynamics. The Data Hub aims to serve both researchers and the public by consolidating and simplifying access to data critical for analysing anti-corruption initiatives and their effectiveness.

Objectives and Features

The Data Hub was designed with several key objectives. The platform enables cross-country evaluations of anti-corruption effectiveness by compiling data suitable as dependent variables, streamlines access to anti-corruption metrics through a single, user-friendly website, incorporates theoretical insights to present data on the drivers and deterrents of corruption, and provides interactive tools for users to explore patterns and trends across countries and regions.

Central to this initiative is addressing the persistent challenge of assessing corruption levels and their evolution by centralising high-quality data and presenting it in an accessible format. The Data Hub employs a structured framework that distinguishes between *direct indicators* and *indirect indicators* (e.g., transparency, regulation, enforcement, internet empowerment, and freedom of expression) to evaluate evolutions over time.

Methodology and Database Structure

The data included in the Data Hub was selected precisely, emphasising theoretical relevance, geographical and temporal scope, and data quality. Key sources include the [Index of Public Integrity](https://corruptionrisk.org/integrity/)¹, [EuroPAM](http://europam.eu/)², the [Transparency Index](https://corruptionrisk.org/transparency/#index)³, the [Corruption Perceptions Index](https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2023)⁴, and procurement data from [OpenTender.eu](https://opentender.eu/start)⁵. Rigorous cleaning, standardisation, and validation processes were undertaken to ensure the data's accuracy and reliability. The final database consists of 42 indicators organised into six theoretical dimensions and is maintained in a relational structure. This approach ensures scalability, flexibility, and the capacity for advanced queries and updates.

Platform Highlights

The Data Hub website offers:

¹ Index of Public Integrity: <https://corruptionrisk.org/integrity/>

² EuroPAM: <http://europam.eu/>

³ Transparency Index: <https://corruptionrisk.org/transparency/#index>

⁴ Corruption Perceptions Index: <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2023>

⁵ OpenTender.eu: <https://opentender.eu/start>

- A **welcoming landing page** that introduces the platform’s objectives, theoretical framework, and datasets.
- An **interactive dashboard** featuring maps, bar charts, and tables that allow users to explore and visualise data dynamically.
- Integration of the “[Follow the Money](https://corruptiondata.eu/follow-the-money/)”⁶ search engine, powered by YouControl's YC World tool, which visualises business connections to uncover potential conflicts of interest and undue influence.

Future Directions

The team is committed to expanding the platform’s reach and functionality by integrating new data sources, enhancing user tools, and incorporating feedback. A comprehensive dissemination strategy will ensure the platform’s visibility and impact among policymakers, researchers, civil society organisations, and development practitioners.

⁶ Follow the Money: <https://corruptiondata.eu/follow-the-money/>

1. CONCEPTUALISING THE DATA HUB

The BridgeGap Data Hub is referenced throughout the Grant Agreement, with its features encompassing a wide range of functionalities. These include serving as a tool for accessing an interoperable set of databases from consortium partners, aggregating data from diverse sources, mapping undue influence, and facilitating ethnographic research to analyse the typologies and operational methods of corrupt actors and networks. The challenge of integrating this many features into a single tool, were duly recognized during the project's kick-off meeting.

As a result, the consortium reassessed the ambitions for the Data Hub. While the objectives outlined in the Grant Agreement were deemed achievable, there was broad agreement that these goals would be better served by clearly distinguishing between two focuses: (1) tracking changes across countries and over time using national-level indicators and (2) mapping corrupt networks and supporting ethnographic research through individual-level indicators and network analysis. The former—creating a repository of consortium datasets and a pooled database for analysing corruption trends across countries and over time—was incorporated into the Data Hub. The latter focus was redirected to the *Follow the Money* initiative.

Additionally, factors such as cybersecurity concerns, technological limitations, user experience, and platform sustainability further reinforced the decision to separate the Data Hub and *Follow the Money*. This decision had a direct impact on the commitments described in the Grant Agreement, leading to the redistribution of components originally associated with the Data Hub across these two distinct tools.

As outlined in this report, the Data Hub is the central data repository for BridgeGap. It serves as both a gateway to datasets generated by the consortium and a tool for visualising direct and indirect corruption indicators across countries and over time. In its first iteration, and in line with the Grant Agreement, the Data Hub offers users access to 42 key indicators, aggregated from over a dozen datasets, such as the Corruption Perceptions Index, EuroPAM and t-index, with options for visualisation and download. The platform is also designed to expand as BridgeGap progresses, and additional data is generated.

Meanwhile, the *Follow the Money* engine focuses on uncovering connections between individuals. As part of this initiative, 15 new datasets—most originally developed under Transparency International's *Integrity Watch* project—have been integrated into YouControl's YC World tool, enhancing its capabilities and in line with the original commitments included in the grant agreement. This tool is expected to be particularly useful for ethnographic research and by offering free access to the YouControl platform, civic journalists will be empowered to conduct their own research as promised in the BridgeGap proposal. **Table 1** below outlines the Grant Agreement commitments and their integration into the respective tools.

The following parts of the report provide an overview of the activities conducted over the past ten months by the Data Hub team, which consisted of members of the Transparency International Secretariat, SAR, LUISS and YouControl (see list of contributors).. They also provide more details on the structure, content and functionality of each of both the Data Hub and the Follow the Money search engine, as well as an overview of the activities envisaged for these products for the remaining duration of the BridgeGap project.

TABLE 1. DISTRIBUTION OF DATA HUB ATTRIBUTES AS PER THE GRANT AGREEMENT ACROSS THE NEWLY CONCEIVED DATA HUB AND FOLLOW THE MONEY TOOLS

Data Hub	Follow the Money
Solve the difficult problem of tracing corruption across time and borders by triangulating objective data.	Pool data and interconnect data repositories from various partners and sources whenever possible (at least 20 new databases will be interconnected for YouControl’s Follow the Money searches).
Create interactive, analytical and research commons like comparative law repositories EU Compass, European Transparency Index.	Enable ethnographic research to investigate the typologies and modus operandi of corrupt actors and networks in three domains (i.e. creation of offshore enabling structures; energy capture; hedge/investment funds and universities) (WP2)
Validate all sources of data pooled by partners in this research effort and solve the problem of eventual data gaps, ensuring that data is sufficient so that by careful triangulation, all research questions can be answered.	Allow the mapping of cross-border corruption and illicit financial flows as well as foreign undue influence in political institutions
Offer an estimation of both unaccountable financial flows and the trend in cross-border corruption (using a gravity model based on the project Data Hub).	Allow civic journalists to conduct searches through search engines made available in the Web Portal developed in WP10.
Data pooling in one hub for use of consortium members the Integrity Watch, T-Index repository of national data, CRF databases, EUROPAM, sanctions, FCPA, OECD Anti-bribery convention cases.	Follow the Money search engines across newly interconnected databases. All its pooled data will be displayed transparently on the website as a Data Hub and will offer end users the same investigation and analytical tools as the project researchers, inviting crowd-sourcing and offering online tutorials.

1. BridgeGap Data Hub

Assessing corruption levels and their evolution over time remains a central challenge in corruption research. While significant progress has been made in quantifying specific forms of corruption—such as bribery in public service delivery or favouritism in public procurement—many other types remain elusive and difficult to measure consistently across countries and over time. Yet, tracking changes in corruption is crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of anti-corruption policies. Since relying on a single indicator is insufficient to capture the complexity and dynamics of corruption, the Data Hub embodies BridgeGap’s solution to this challenge.

In line with the project’s objectives, the Data Hub is a repository of relevant information meant to provide objective, reliable, and actionable metrics of corruption. Its core objectives include:

- **Identifying and compiling data** that can serve as dependent variables in cross-country evaluations of the effectiveness of anti-corruption
- **Simplify access to relevant anti-corruption data** by centralising existing metrics into one website, creating space for future metrics developed throughout the duration of the BridgeGap project and making this information publicly accessible.
- **Presenting data on the enabling and disabling factors for anti-corruption** in a way that reflects the latest theoretical insights in the field.
- **Offering visualisation tools** that allow users to explore patterns and trends across countries.

Additionally, the Data Hub seeks to combine robust measurement methodologies with tested theoretical insights to pilot a more comprehensive framework to understand and monitor corruption.

2.1 Theoretical approach

With the growing number of corruption indicators, it becomes increasingly challenging to keep track of them, understand their differences, and determine which is best suited to achieve a specific objective. For this reason, the Data Hub was conceived as more than a simple repository of corruption or governance-related data. The team recognised that for the site to add value for researchers and non-specialized audiences alike, the data needed to be presented in an intuitive manner that also helped users understand the relationship between indicators, what they measure and why they are included in a framework meant to capture corruption.

To achieve the ambition outlined above and distinguish the new site from existing platforms—such as the [Quality of Government \(QoG\) Data Finder](https://datafinder.qog.gu.se)⁷ or [Our World in Data](https://ourworldindata.org/)⁸, which provide access to extensive governance-related indicators, or those focused on specific indicators—the Data Hub adopts a unique approach: it integrates the latest theoretical insights from anti-corruption research to provide an intuitive

⁷ Quality of Government (QoG) Data Finder: <https://datafinder.qog.gu.se>

⁸ Our World Data: <https://ourworldindata.org/>

user experience and guide users effectively through the data. **Figure 1** provides a graphic representation of the logic that was mainstreamed throughout the Data Hub and utilised to classify the data.

FIGURE 1. DATA HUB FRAMEWORK FOR MEASURING CORRUPTION

More specifically, the Data Hub is structured around a framework that distinguishes between

- **direct indicators:** a range of global and regional indices that directly assess the prevalence and impact of corruption within countries and
- **indirect indicators:** metrics or proxies that are seen either as potential enabling or disabling factors for corruption to occur.

The indirect indicators of corruption, which make up most of the data included in the Data Hub, are further divided into five categories that align with factors identified as effective elements of a robust system to control corruption, including transparency, regulation, enforcement, internet empowerment and freedom of expression (see **Table 2**). In general, the indirect indicators will focus on capturing risks and responses to corruption or so-called “enabling” and “disabling”. Through this framework, the Data Hub’s structure will be firmly grounded on insights from the specialised literature and will build on similar work done by relevant policy players, including the [United Nations Statistical Framework to Measure Corruption](https://www.unodc.org/documents/data-and-analysis/statistics/corruption/UNODC%20Statistical%20Framework%20to%20measure%20corruption.pdf)⁹.

TABLE 2. CATEGORISATION OF INDIRECT CORRUPTION INDICATORS IN THE DATA HUB.

Category	Explanation
Transparency	Covers various aspects of transparency in government operations, ensuring that key information about finances, administration, judicial

⁹ *United Nations Statistical Framework to Measure Corruption:* [https://www.unodc.org/documents/data-and-analysis/statistics/corruption/UNODC Statistical Framework to measure corruption.pdf](https://www.unodc.org/documents/data-and-analysis/statistics/corruption/UNODC%20Statistical%20Framework%20to%20measure%20corruption.pdf)

	proceedings, and elections is accessible and understandable to the public.
Freedom of Expression	Provides data on media freedom and civil society's ability to operate freely. It covers legal protections and real-world challenges to expression across various contexts.
Regulation	Covers legal frameworks and mechanisms aimed at enforcing transparency, accountability, and the fight against corruption.
Internet Empowerment	Assesses the effectiveness of digital platforms and services in promoting transparency, empowering citizens to access public information, and engaging with governance. It also examines the extent to which these tools are utilized by the public.
Enforcement	Focuses on efforts to enforce anti-corruption laws and policies at both the national and international levels.

2.2 Data selection

As the team established the theoretical foundations of the Data Hub, it was equally crucial to drive progress in data collection efforts. To differentiate the Data Hub from other platforms, the team prioritised data quality over quantity, ensuring that every dataset contributes meaningfully to enhancing understanding of corruption dynamics across countries and over time. The first step in this process was the careful selection of relevant data sources—a critical task to ensure that all included data aligns with the Hub's overarching goals. The guiding principles to include data in the Data Hub included:

- **Theoretical relevance:** data was chosen based on its alignment with the specific goals of the BridgeGap project and its ability to capture or help explain the levels of corruption across countries. Data was also selected to cover various relevant variables, ensuring that the Data Hub contains direct measurements of corruption and enabling and disabling factors.
- **Geographical and time coverage:** Unfortunately, many corruption indicators, particularly direct metrics, are not updated regularly or are only available for a small number of countries. However, given the project's ambition to contribute to the study of corruption trends, the data included in the hub needed to cover more than one point in time and as many BridgeGap countries as possible. **Annex 1** provides the full overview of the countries included in the Data Hub.
- **Data quality and actionability:** Emphasis was placed on the methodological soundness and reliability of the data, as well as on its actionability for policy.

The main sources of data identified to feed the Data Hub, which also includes indicators produced by the BridgeGap consortium partners, include: the Index of Public Integrity (IPI), the European Public Accountability Mechanisms (EuroPAM), the Transparency Index (t-index), the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI), and OpenTender (OpenTender.eu), among others (see **Table 3**).

It is important to note that, throughout this process, the team had to exclude specific data sources they had hoped to include in the Data Hub due to various constraints. These challenges included licensing restrictions

(e.g. [FCPA sanctions data by Stanford Law School and Sullivan and Cromwell LLP](#)¹⁰), lack of data for a sizeable number of countries in the BridgeGap sample (e.g. OECD anti-bribery sanctions), lack of enough comparable data over time (e.g. [Transparency International's Global Corruption Barometer](#)¹¹) and lack of updated indicator versions (e.g. crony capitalism index and wealth concentration data). While it may not be possible to address the gaps left by the omission of these indicators in the short term, the Data Hub team is committed to bridging them through alternative data sources and official access-to-information requests in the future.

TABLE 3. DATA HUB'S MAIN SOURCES OF DATA.

Name	Description
Index of Public Integrity	The Index of Public Integrity (IPI) is a comprehensive measure designed to assess the integrity and capacity of a country's public administration and institutions to prevent corruption and ensure good governance. The IPI focuses on the structural and institutional factors that contribute to or inhibit public integrity, providing a detailed look at the underlying conditions that facilitate or hinder corruption control. The IPI's score considers six components: judicial independence, budget transparency, administrative burden, trade openness, e-citizenship and press freedom.
EuroPAM	EuroPAM is a comprehensive assessment designed to provide detailed information on various accountability mechanisms across European countries. It is primarily used to determine the strength of a country's legal framework vis-a-vis international best practices in areas that are deemed relevant to prevent and detect corruption such as access to information, political finance, and asset disclosure, among others.
Transparency Index	The Transparency Index (t-index) is a novel indicator that captures real (de facto) instead of just formal (de jure) transparency. The index and its disaggregated components help identify concrete gaps in the availability of public information.
Corruption Perceptions Index	The Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) is an annual index published by Transparency International. It ranks countries around the world based on their perceived levels of public sector corruption. The index is based on the assessments of 13 different sources and is widely regarded as one of the leading global indicators of corruption.
OpenTender.eu	OpenTender.eu is an online platform designed to enhance transparency and accountability in public procurement across Europe. It aggregates and analyses data on public tenders, providing insights into how public funds are spent and helping to identify potential issues such as corruption, inefficiency, and lack of competition. F
Press Freedom Index	The purpose of the World Press Freedom Index is to compare the level of freedom enjoyed by journalists and media at the country and territory level.

¹⁰ FCPA sanctions data by Stanford Law School and Sullivan and Cromwell LLP: <https://fcpa.stanford.edu/about-the-fcpac.html#about>

¹¹ Transparency International's Global Corruption Barometer: <https://www.transparency.org/en/gcb>

2.3 Database construction

After selecting the data for the initial iteration of the Data Hub, the next critical step was to aggregate and compile it into a cohesive dataset that forms the platform's foundation. This process was crucial to ensure the data was clean, standardised, and ready for seamless integration into the Data Hub. Additionally, scalability was a top priority. Since the Data Hub will evolve as BridgeGap advances, it was essential to design a data structure that could be easily updated and to establish a standardised template for consistent use by all project researchers in the future. As part of this process, the team engaged in the following activities:

- **Format standardisation:** ensuring that data across different datasets follows a consistent structure and format. This involved creating a standardised template for data collection and agreeing on a structure in which all project data will be reported.
- **Data Cleaning:** In this step, any errors, inconsistencies, or missing values in the data were addressed. This involved removing duplicates, correcting formatting issues, filling in missing information where possible, or flagging missing data points for further review.
- **Data update:** In some cases, new data was collected to ensure the latest available information would be accessible through the Data Hub.
- **Metadata Creation:** Metadata was added to describe the characteristics and context of each dataset. This includes source information, date ranges, and data definitions to ensure that users of the Data Hub can understand and appropriately interpret the data.

Cleaning, standardising, and merging datasets proved to be highly time- and resource-intensive. This was largely because most sources were not formatted as time series data. Instead, they were often structured to provide observations for multiple countries at a single point in time, or when a temporal component was included, it was typically limited to data for one country at a time. As an example of the challenges faced by the team, the EuroPAM data was originally scattered across a total of 23 files, one for each thematic area (e.g., political financing, financial disclosure, conflict of interest, freedom of information and public procurement) per year (2012, 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2020). Furthermore, the files available for download contained limited information about the construction of some sub-indices, provided no unique country or variable identifiers, had no information about the range of the scale or the types of variables, and did not contain usable variable labels. Additionally, some information required to create the metadata was scattered across individual country tabs. Similarly, extracting public procurement-related data from OpenTender.eu implied downloading information from over 35 national portals to be merged afterwards into a cross-country time series dataset.

The final Data Hub database contains **42 indicators** (see **Annex 2**) allocated across the **6 theoretical dimensions** defined in the previous section, i.e., corruption measurements, transparency, regulation, enforcement, internet empowerment, and freedom of expression. To simplify the identification of relevant indicators, the team categorised the data into specific sub-components. While the six theoretical dimensions are seen as fixed, sub-components can be adjusted—added or removed—as new data is incorporated. These sub-components are designed to give users greater clarity on the relevance of specific indicators and their connection to corruption. **Annex 3** provides the complete list of sub-components.

To ensure the scalability and flexibility of the BridgeGap dataset, the team favoured a relational approach. As a result, the structure of the table containing the indicators is quite simple and consists of just eight fields:

- **ISO3:** provides the standardised three-letter code to identify countries,
- **Year:** denotes the year that the data corresponds to,
- **Indicator_ID:** contains the unique label for the indicator,
- **Value:** includes the value of the indicator for the assigned year,
- **Dataset:** contains information related to the source of the data,
- **Themes:** links the data to one of the six theoretical dimensions of the data framework,
- **Component:** assigns each data point to one of the components designed to provide more information about the indicator's relevance and simplify navigation.

FIGURE 2. DATA HUB SUB-COMPONENTS

By relying on a relational database structure (see **Figure 2**), it is easier to ensure data integrity since the relationships can help enforce rules that maintain consistency across the data and changes to one table do not require re-designing the entire database. This also allows for better metadata integration and makes it easier to correct labels or add information in the future without touching the data itself. This solution is also more suitable for handling larger amounts of data and will be easier to maintain and update as the BridgeGap project progresses and new data becomes available. Finally, the relational model provides the flexibility required to enable more complex queries and analyses, a feature that will be integrated into future iterations of the Data Hub.

2.4 Quality control and testing

After completing the data collection and compiling it into the agreed-upon template, the team undertook a thorough review to ensure accuracy and consistency, verifying that the values in the BridgeGap dataset matched the original sources. During this testing and quality control phase, the team also developed an internal platform to visualise the data. This platform enabled the identification of potential missing values and informed decisions about the most effective visual representations to include in the final Data Hub. Additionally, it allowed the team to test the usability of the structure, which was organised by theoretical dimensions, themes, sub-components, and indicators, ensuring it was both intuitive and practical. **Figure 2** showcases the internal testing platform, which remains connected to the same dataset powering the public website. This integration will enable the team to pilot and refine new features in the future.

At this stage of the process, the team concluded that the more than 400 binary variables, primarily sourced from the EuroPAM data, contributed limited value to the overall Data Hub. Rather than enhancing the user experience, these variables risked overwhelming users and complicating identifying relevant indicators. Additionally, the visualisation options for binary data were found to be less engaging and ineffective in conveying meaningful insights. In the spirit of having a more parsimonious set of indicators with the potential to provide a better user experience and a clearer picture of corruption across countries, the team favoured the solution of not including binary data as part of the hub.

FIGURE 3. DATA HUB INTERNAL TESTING AND VISUALISATION PLATFORM

Alongside the data quality checks, the team ensured the metadata was comprehensive and meticulously prepared. This involved verifying that all data labels were accurate, consistent, and easy to understand and that accompanying explanations provided clear context for users. Special attention was given to documenting the data sources, ensuring proper attribution, and preparing citations in line with academic best practices. These details were organised to be seamlessly displayed on the Data Hub, ensuring full transparency in the provenance of the data, allowing users to trace the origins of the data, review the relevant methodological documents and foster trust and credibility in the platform.

2.5 Data Hub structure, design and functionality

The final stage in developing the Data Hub was designing the website itself. Structurally, the Data Hub is composed of two key elements. The first is a **landing page** that offers a comprehensive introduction to the platform, including an overview of its purpose, the theoretical framework guiding the organisation of data, a summary of the information available, and links to original datasets produced by the BridgeGap consortium. The second element is an **interactive dashboard**, which empowers users to explore and visualise the various indicators, providing a dynamic and engaging way to interact with the data.

FIGURE 4. NESTED VIEW OF INDICATORS CONTAINED IN THE DATA HUB BY THEME AND COMPONENT.

Theme Name	Component Name	Indicator Link
∨ Corruption Measures		
Corruption Measures	Public Integrity	Index of Public Integrity
Corruption Measures	Single bidding	Bidder number score
Corruption Measures	Corruption Perception	Corruption Perception Index - Score
> Enforcement		
> Freedom of Expression		
> Internet Empowerment		
∨ Regulation		
Regulation	Freedom of Information Regulation	Freedom of Information Score (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Political Financing Regulation	Political Financing Score (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Public Procurement Regulation	Public Procurement Score (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Financial Disclosure Regulation	Financial Disclosure Score (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Freedom of Information Regulation	Scope and coverage (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Freedom of Information Regulation	Information access and release (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Freedom of Information Regulation	Exceptions and Overrides (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Freedom of Information Regulation	Sanctions for non-compliance (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Freedom of Information Regulation	Monitoring and Oversight (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Political Financing Regulation	Bans and limits on private income (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Political Financing Regulation	Public funding (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Political Financing Regulation	Regulations on spending (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Political Financing Regulation	Reporting, oversight and sanctions (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Public Procurement Regulation	Scope and coverage (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Public Procurement Regulation	Information availability (EUROPAM)
Regulation	Public Procurement Regulation	Evaluation (EUROPAM)

The Data Hub's landing page¹² is accessible through the main BridgeGap website and is designed to “integrate with the BridgeGap “look and feel”. The page is organised into three primary sections for clarity and functionality.

- **Top section:** This section features a welcome message accompanied by the diagram introduced earlier (**Figure 1**), which acts as an intuitive gateway to the dashboard. Users can interact with the diagram by clicking on its various sections, redirecting them to the dashboard and the corresponding list of indicators under the selected theme.
- **Middle section:** Designed as an inventory of indicators, this section provides a hierarchical list of all data, organised by theme and component. Users can expand or collapse these lists to explore the indicators under each category. Each list includes a concise description summarising its content, aligned with the descriptions in Table 1. To enhance usability, the data hierarchy is visually represented using nested views to clearly illustrate relationships (**Figure 4**).
- **Bottom section:** This part of the site is conceived as a place where other relevant BridgeGap and partner datasets can be accessed and downloaded. While the Data Hub's geographical coverage is limited to 40 countries, many of the datasets used as sources of information include data for a broader

Additionally, as part of the interactive dashboard, users will be able to display each indicator geographically (on a map), as a bar chart to more easily compare scores across country, or as a table to see all available data by country over time. **Figure 5** shows the mock-up of the Data Hub and the interactive dashboard.

¹² The Data Hub was staged for development at <https://bg-dh2.evidence.app/> and openly accessible here <http://datahub.corruptiondata.eu/> from 29/11/2024.

FIGURE 5. MOCK-UP OF THE DATA HUB LANDING PAGE AND INTERACTIVE DASHBOARD

DATAHUB

Welcome to the DataHub of BridgeGap. This resource includes data repositories and analytic tools, as follows:

- All current databases used for research in BridgeGap pooled by partners, at country and multicountry level
- EU Compass analytical database, pooling data at national level following the UNODC Statistical Framework model (to be completed by end 2025, adding Europam.eu and EUCAL.eu data on preventive and criminal regulation against corruption)
- [Follow the Money](#) search engine powered and hosted by YouControl, a BridgeGap partner

How does EU Compass work?

Control of corruption is the capacity of a society to constrain public authorities to act for general social welfare and not for the particular benefit of private individuals, groups or networks connected to the office holders. Control of corruption results from a balance between opportunities for corruption and constraints, posed by societies and states. We proxy those here as parts of a public integrity framework consisting of Transparency, Regulation, Enforcement, Freedom of Expression and Internet Empowerment. We also include direct indicators of corruption.

This website covers 41 countries, including EU Member States and accession countries. However, the coverage of indicators may be dissimilar, especially on direct indicators.

As of November 2024 EU Compass is already ready to use due to pooling of a first set of data from consortium members, although it will grow considerably over the next two years with granular regulation and enforcement data.

Full Indicator List

Theme Name	Component Name	Indicator Link
> Corruption Measures		
> Enforcement		
> Freedom of Expression		
> Internet Empowerment		
> Regulation		
> Transparency		

Corruption Perception Index - Score 2023

Perceived levels of corruption in the public sector

[Corruption Measures / Corruption Perception](#)

Dataset: [Corruption Perceptions Index](#)

Select Year: 2023

2. BridgeGap's Follow the Money

The Data Hub described in the previous section will enable users to access unprecedented knowledge about corruption and assess the impact of specific anti-corruption policies across countries over time. However, part of the BridgeGap proposal also described the Data Hub as a tool that would “enable ethnographic research to investigate the typologies and modus operandi of corrupt actors” and facilitate “forensic analysis via social network analysis and specific investigation software”.

While the original idea was to leverage YouControl's expertise to integrate a platform like [YC World](#)¹³ into the Data Hub, the technical team raised several risks and challenges that would have been difficult to mitigate, including:

- **Compatibility issues and cost:** The platform would have required a specific technology and infrastructure to work correctly on the BridgeGap website and ensure seamless integration and compatibility with the source. The type of infrastructure needed would have been too expensive to obtain.
- **Maintenance complexity:** Since many sources that feed into YC World's datasets are updated regularly and even daily, the website would have required constant attention. Keeping the cloned platform updated with new features or patches would have required significant effort or led to bugs and inconsistencies.
- **Security risks:** Given the nature of the platform and its objective of helping trace opaque business links and risky connections, targeted hacking attempts or cyberattacks could not be ruled out. While YouControl's existing server and security infrastructure consider these risks, it would have been impossible for the BridgeGap project to guarantee the necessary level of security.
- **Redundancy and differentiation issues:** Cloning the content of the YC World platform or simply providing a new interface to interact with it on the BridgeGap website offered little added value, and the new tool would have struggled to remain competitive and attractive to users.
- **Sustainability:** Developing tools to help with ethnographic research and focus on individual-level connections is complex, labour-intensive, and time-consuming. Developing such a tool from scratch just for the BridgeGap project would likely have produced a platform incapable of competing against existing ones, such as YouControl's tools, [OCCRP's ALEPH](#)¹⁴, or [Moody's Orbis](#)¹⁵. This would have made the platform's sustainability a challenge after the project's finalisation.

The team also highlighted that combining indicators with varying levels of granularity and distinct technical and analytical requirements into a single platform would be counterproductive from a user experience point

¹³ YC World: <https://youcontrol.world/>

¹⁴ OCCRP's ALEPH: <https://aleph.occrp.org/entities/icij-100313941.984a8f7185310bc095ba4a545a3a8f386811a5b7>

¹⁵ [Moody's Orbis](#)

of view. Since each data type demand is geared towards answering very different research questions and answering those questions often requires a very different set of analytical and visualisation tools, the consortium agreed that developing two separate platforms would be a more cost-effective, sustainable, and practical solution. This solution also helps to ensure that the unique needs of their respective datasets are appropriately addressed.

To meet the project's ambitions while accounting for the challenges described above, the team's solution was to keep the Data Hub as a central repository of data and a visualisation tool for national-level indicators but embed a "Follow the Money" search engine, powered by the YouControl's YC World tool directly into the BridgeGap website.

3.1 Building the "Follow the Money" search engine

Follow the Money is a search engine enabled by YouControl. This BridgeGap consortium partner builds on its proprietary [YC World](#) platform. It allows users to research potential conflicts of interest and undue influence by pooling information from almost 300 data sources and visualising business links between companies and individuals. The sources of data that allow YC World to document over 150 million connections between more than 172 million entities, 77 million people and 85 million companies across 74 countries include registers of commerce, lobbying registers, party donations, procurements allocations, financial disclosures and sanctions lists from the European Union, the United Kingdom, Ukraine, Russia, Moldova, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Belarus, among others.

By embedding access to YouControl's YC World database directly through the BridgeGap website, the project sets a new standard in the transparency, interactivity and impact of corruption research, as it allows users to engage with the same investigation and analytical tools used by researchers in the project. To make this possible, the YouControl team provided an API endpoint with a unique key authorisation token for the BridgeGap project. It is worth noting, however, that the search engine embedded in the BridgeGap website is only meant to serve as a gateway to the full capabilities of YouControl's platform. Users on the BridgeGap website can use the follow the money search engine (see **Figure 6**) to search for companies or individuals based on name, phone number, email, website, address or tax number.

FIGURE 6. FOLLOW THE MONEY SEARCH ENGINE

Using the API created by YouControl enables the search engine to show the number of records where the term entered by the user was found across all the linked databases and whether the hits were connected to an individual or a company. To access the detailed results, however, the user needs to register for the YC World platform. The search results also display the links to access YC World and register to use the full array of services the platform offers. Once users are logged into the YC World portal, they can continue their search for potential connections between individuals and companies across all datasets through an array of tools

and features, including the visualisation of links on the infinite graph to quickly identify dependencies between entities and find hidden insights (see **Figure 7**), the ability to create custom entities and connection, and the ability to automatically translate information into English and transliterate names, which is particularly useful when dealing with different alphabets.

FIGURE 7. EXAMPLE OF YC WORLD'S NETWORK ANALYSIS HIGHLIGHTING CROSS-BORDER LINKS BETWEEN BUSINESSES AND INDIVIDUALS

It is worth noting that the YouControl will be able to use their analytical systems to provide detailed information on the number of users and access requests received as a way to identify whether the users are part of the BridgeGap community.

3.2 Strengthening YC World's and "Follow the Money" abilities

Finally, focusing the project's resources on improving the YouControl platform and making it available to researchers and the public for the project's duration was seen as a more sustainable solution, helping ensure the platform's survival beyond BridgeGap. Instead, the focus of the project can be shifted towards continuous improvement of the platform through the incorporation of new sources of data. Along this line, YouControl collaborated closely with Transparency International to integrate some of the data from the Integrity Watch initiative into the YC World platform. As of November 2024, a total of **17 datasets** have been added, including: Ukrainian state registry (full daily updates), Romanian National Trade Register, Cyprus Register of Companies, Malta Business Registry (MBR), Bulgarian Commercial register, Latvia company registry, list of current Members of the European Parliament, registered EU lobby organisations, European Parliament lobby meetings, European Commission lobby meetings, Dutch, Latvian and Italian political party donations, UK State registry (Company House), Bulgarian Persons of Interest, Russia Federal Tax Registry (EGRUL), and Russia Unified State Register of Individual Entrepreneurs (EGRIP). The list of websites added to the Follow the Money platform as part of the BridgeGap project will be constantly updated on the website to acknowledge the project's contribution (see **Figure 8**).

FIGURE 8. LOST OF DATASETS ADDED TO YC WORLD PLATFORM AS PART OF THE BRIDGE GAP PROJECT

Follow the Money is a search engine enabled by the **Youcontrol**, a **BridgeGap** partner organization, on top of their **YC World pooled database**.

The search engine enables investigating beneficial ownership (who really owns a company) and undue corrupt influence (links between public authority holders, directly or through their proxies and businesses) by uncovering business links between companies and individuals, searching mostly in registers of commerce from the *European Union, United Kingdom, Ukraine, Russia, Moldova, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Belarus*.

Track relevant connections between subjects using either names of individuals or businesses.

To use the search engine, you need to have login credentials that you can obtain by writing [here](#).

This demo shows how you can use the search engine, including saving your favorite results for future reference.

Person search:

- Full name.
- First name.
- Taxpayer number.
- Address of registration.
- Email.

Company search:

- Company name (original or English version).
- Complete name of a legal entity.
- Short name of a legal entity.
- Company phone number.
- Corporate registration email.
- Company's website.
- Legal entity's address of registration.

See here the [list of the available data sources](#).

Within the BridgeGap project, the following databases have been added:

1. Ukrainian state registry (full daily updates)
2. Romanian National Trade Register
3. Cyprus Register of Companies
4. Malta Business Registry (MBR)
5. Bulgarian Commercial register
6. Latvia company registry
7. List of current MEPs
8. Registered EU lobby organisations
9. European Parliament lobby meetings
10. European Commission lobby meetings
11. Political party finance (Netherlands)
12. Political party finance (Latvia)

The list of databases is being updated on an ongoing basis.

BRIDGING THE GAPS
IN EVIDENCE, REGULATION
AND IMPACT
OF ANTI-CORRUPTION
POLICIES

PRIVACY | COOKIES | SITEMAP

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Governance

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3. Next steps and future of the Data Hub

As the BridgeGap Data Hub moves forward following its initial launch, the team is dedicated to ensuring its continued growth, improvement, and visibility. This next phase focuses on three key areas: testing and user feedback, data hub expansion, and dissemination. These efforts aim to refine the platform, enhance its data offerings, and reach broader audiences to maximise its impact. By engaging users, incorporating new data, and promoting the platform effectively, the Data Hub will remain a valuable and evolving resource for understanding and addressing corruption dynamics worldwide.

Each of these areas plays a vital role in ensuring that the Data Hub meets the needs of its current users but also adapts and expands to address emerging trends and insights. Below, we outline the plans for the Data Hub.

4.1 Testing and user feedback

In the coming months, the BridgeGap Data Hub team will focus on gathering user feedback to inform potential improvements and refinements to the platform. Engaging with users is crucial to ensure that the Data Hub meets their needs and provides an intuitive, efficient, and valuable experience. Feedback will be collected through various channels, including user testing sessions, surveys, and direct interactions, enabling the team to identify areas for enhancement and incorporate suggestions into future platform iterations. As part of this process, the team will also engage national chapters from across the TI Movement, as well as students from the universities included in the BridgeGap consortium.

4.2 Data Hub and Follow the Money Expansions

Additionally, the team will continue to expand the Data Hub by integrating relevant data sources that were unavailable at the time of the initial launch. Many of these sources required formal requests through official channels to access and were not immediately ready for inclusion. As this data becomes available, it will be carefully reviewed, cleaned, and duly formatted before being incorporated into the platform. This ongoing effort will ensure that the Data Hub remains a comprehensive and reliable resource for understanding corruption dynamics across countries and over time.

As the BridgeGap project progresses and delivers new datasets such as the expanded version of EuroPAM, the new assessment of criminal legislation against corruption (EUCAL) or as new editions of existing tools are released, they will be included in the platform to reflect the latest trends. The platform is designed to be scalable and adaptable, enabling the integration of emerging insights and innovative indicators produced by the project. This iterative approach ensures that the Data Hub remains at the forefront of anti-corruption research, providing users with up-to-date, high-quality data that supports evidence-based decision-making and policy development. The team's commitment to continuous improvement will ensure that the Data Hub remains a dynamic and impactful tool throughout the project and beyond.

Additionally, the teams at Transparency International and YouControl have agreed that Transparency International will promote the Follow the Money tool and the YC World platform among relevant national chapters. They will also encourage these chapters to identify and suggest potential data sources that could enhance the platform's content and ability to track business links. However, the inclusion of such platforms depends on YouControl's final technical and feasibility assessment.

4.3 Dissemination

The BridgeGap communications team is also developing a comprehensive strategy to disseminate the Data Hub and maximise its visibility among relevant audiences. As part of this effort, the team has already identified several opportunities to showcase the platform, including upcoming academic conferences, policy workshops, and networking events in the governance and anti-corruption sectors. By targeting key stakeholders such as policymakers, researchers, civil society organisations, and development practitioners, the communications strategy aims to ensure that the Data Hub reaches those who can most effectively use its insights to drive change. These efforts will be complemented by digital outreach through social media campaigns, newsletters, and partnerships with influential platforms.

Annex 1. BridgeGap / Data Hub country coverage

AUT: Austria	MLT: Malta
BEL: Belgium	NLD: Netherlands
BGR: Bulgaria	NOR: Norway
HRV: Croatia	POL: Poland
CYP: Cyprus	PRT: Portugal
CZE: Czechia	ROU: Romania
DNK: Denmark	SRB: Serbia
EST: Estonia	SVK: Slovakia
FIN: Finland	SVN: Slovenia
FRA: France	ESP: Spain
GEO: Georgia	SWE: Sweden
DEU: Germany	CHE: Switzerland
GRC: Greece	GBR: United Kingdom
HUN: Hungary	ALB: Albania
ISL: Iceland	BIH: Bosnia and Herzegovina
IRL: Ireland	MDA: Moldova
ITA: Italy	MNE: Montenegro
LVA: Latvia	MKD: North Macedonia
LTU: Lithuania	UKR: Ukraine
LUX: Luxembourg	TUR: Türkiye

Annex 2. Complete List of Indicators in the BridgeGap dataset

INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	COMPONENT
Administrative Transparency	This indicator consists of the standardized sum of individual scores for relevant items in the de facto Transparency Index	Administrative Transparency
Conflict of Interest Score	Strength of the legal framework on conflict of interest	Conflict of Interest Regulation
Restrictions	This indicator captures whether the existing legislation restricts specific variations of conflict of interest such as accepting gifts, private firm/stock ownership, holding government contracts, etc.	Conflict of Interest Regulation
Sanctions	This indicator captures whether the existing legislation stipulates fines, penal sanctions, or administrative sanctions for violations of COI regulations restricting behaviour	Conflict of Interest Regulation
Monitoring and Oversight	This indicator captures whether the existing legislation incorporates designates specific monitoring and enforcement bodies for matters of conflict of interest.	Conflict of Interest Regulation
Corruption Perception Index - Score	Perceived levels of corruption in the public sector	Corruption Perception
E-Citizenship	Simple mean of standardized values of the percentage in populations of fixed broadband subscriptions, Internet users, and Facebook users	Enlightened Citizens
Online Services	The score is based on the Online Services Index, integrated in the UN E-Government Development Index, which measures the scope and quality of online services	E-Services
Total score for de facto transparency	This score captures the existence of online portals to access relevant government information. It evaluates 14 different categories ranging from supreme court rulings, government expenditures and registers of commerce, to procurement information, mining concessions and financial disclosure of politicians.	Electoral Transparency
Financial Disclosure Score	Strength of the legal framework on financial disclosure for politicians	Financial Disclosure Regulation
Financial Disclosure for Head of State	This indicator evaluates various aspects of financial disclosure for Heads of State, including the items required to be disclosed, the frequency of filing, the sanctions for non-compliance, the mechanisms for monitoring and oversight, and public access to the declarations	Financial Disclosure Regulation
Financial Disclosure for Ministers	This indicator evaluates various aspects of financial disclosure for Ministers, including the items required to be disclosed, the frequency of filing, the sanctions for non-compliance, the mechanisms for monitoring and oversight, and public access to the declarations	Financial Disclosure Regulation
Financial Disclosure for Members of Parliament	This indicator evaluates various aspects of financial disclosure for members of Parliament, including the items required to be disclosed, the frequency of filing, the sanctions for non-compliance, the mechanisms for monitoring and oversight, and public access to the declarations	Financial Disclosure Regulation

Financial Disclosure for Civil servants	This indicator evaluates various aspects of financial disclosure for civil servants, including the items required to be disclosed, the frequency of filing, the sanctions for non-compliance, the mechanisms for monitoring and oversight, and public access to the declarations	Financial Disclosure Regulation
Freedom of Information Score	Strength of the legal framework on access to information	Freedom of Information Regulation
Scope and coverage	This indicator assesses the scope of public information disclosure, including the coverage of both public and private sectors, and the access to specific documents, whether subject to reactive and/or proactive disclosure	Freedom of Information Regulation
Information access and release	This indicator evaluates existing procedures to access public information and the deadlines for its release	Freedom of Information Regulation
Exceptions and Overrides	This indicator assesses exemptions to disclosure and the availability of appeals processes	Freedom of Information Regulation
Sanctions for non-compliance	This indicator assesses the presence of specified sanctions for violations of disclosure requirements, including administrative sanctions, fines, and criminal sanctions	Freedom of Information Regulation
Monitoring and Oversight	This indicator evaluates the existence of institutional mechanisms to support the implementation of disclosure requirements, including the mandatory appointment of information officers in public agencies, the designation of a public body responsible for applying sanctions, the presence of a public body dedicated to public outreach, the establishment of a nodal agency for RTI implementation support and compliance, the legal specification of the Ombudsman's involvement in implementation, and the requirement for reporting data and/or implementation.	Freedom of Information Regulation
Budget Transparency	This Indicator represents the mean value of several questions from the Open Budget Survey, measuring transparency in the Executive's Budget Proposal	Fiscal Transparency
Fiscal Transparency (T-Index)	A composite indicator derived from the T-Index assessing the online availability of public expenditure information.	Fiscal Transparency
Transparency Index (Total Score)	The T-Index provides a score that measures the real (de facto) and legal (de jure) transparency of governments. It evaluates the availability, accessibility, and comprehensiveness of key public information required to deter corruption.	Government Transparency
Transparency Index (%)	The Transparency Index score represented as a percentage.	Government Transparency
Cross-border corruption cases initiated	The number of cross-border initiated cases involving firms and foreign public officials by country. The dataset compiles cases from sources like TRACE Compendium, DOJ, SEC, and others. The data is an aggregate value of all years until 2022.	International Enforcement
Cross-border corruption cases concluded	The number of cross-border initiated cases involving firms and foreign public officials by country. The dataset compiles cases from sources like TRACE Compendium, DOJ, SEC, and others. The data is an aggregate value of all years until 2022.	International Enforcement

Convictions against heads of governments	convictions of political leaders who served as heads of government, between 1946 and 2020. To be included, leaders must have been convicted by a domestic civil court after holding office. The dataset excludes convictions by foreign, international, or military courts, as well as impeachments and removals from office.	International Enforcement
Judicial Independence	This indicator captures judicial independence in a country, based on responses from the World Economic Forum's Global Competitiveness Dataset	Judicial Independence
Judicial Transparency (T-index)	A composite indicator derived from the T-Index assessing the online availability of national legislation, Supreme Court decisions, and hearing schedules.	Judicial Transparency
Total score for de jure transparency	This score captures the government's commitment to transparency as per the country's legislation and international agreements. It looks at 6 different categories including the country's ratification of the United Nations convention against Corruption, the existence of a freedom of information law, and participation in initiatives such as the Open Government Partnership.	Public Accountability
Press Freedom Index	A score out of 100 assessing the degree of freedom enjoyed by journalists	Press Freedom
Political Financing Score	Strength of the legal framework on campaign and political financing	Political Finance Regulation
Bans and limits on private income	This indicator captures whether the existing legislation contemplates bans on private donations, including from foreign interests, corporations, trade unions, and anonymous sources.	Political Finance Regulation
Public funding	This indicator captures whether the existing legislation incorporates provisions to determine eligibility for public funding to political parties and how public funding is allocated. Additionally, the indicator considers whether public funding to political parties incorporates provisions to foster gender equality among political parties and candidates.	Political Finance Regulation
Regulations on spending	This indicator captures whether the existing legislation incorporates limits on spending and bans certain expenditures including vote-buying or the use of state resources to favour or disadvantage specific political parties or candidates.	Political Finance Regulation
Reporting, oversight and sanctions	This indicator captures whether the existing legislation defines specific reporting standards for political parties and campaign expenditures, as well as the existence of an adequate institutional framework to examine financial reports, investigate violations, and sanction political parties in case of infractions.	Political Finance Regulation
Index of Public Integrity	The IPI is based on 6 proxy indicators associated with constraints and opportunities of corruption	Public Integrity
Public Procurement Score	Strength of the legal framework on public procurement	Public Procurement Regulation
Scope and coverage	This indicator captures mainly the existing thresholds above which the public procurement regulation applies in different sectors and types of products.	Public Procurement Regulation

Information availability	This indicator captures the amount of information available online to trace the different stages of the procurement process, from tendering to contracting.	Public Procurement Regulation
Evaluation	This indicator captures whether the existing legislation establishes specific criteria to evaluate the bids received and avoid preferential treatment. This includes, among others, reasons for exclusion, clauses that favour national companies over international ones.	Public Procurement Regulation
Open competition	This indicator captures the extent to which the existing legal framework in a country helps guarantee open and competitive procurement procedures by ensuring the publication of the terms of reference, requiring a minimum number of bidders, and defining the minimum number of days that bidding processes remain open.	Public Procurement Regulation
Institutional arrangements	This indicator captures whether the existing legislation in a country establishes an institutional framework to regulate public procurement and process complaints.	Public Procurement Regulation
Political Transparency (T-Index)	A composite indicator derived from the T-Index assessing the availability of financial disclosures and conflict of interest disclosures of public officials	Political Transparency
Bidder number score	Share of public tenders that received more than one bid	Single Bidding
Share of wealth held by top 1%	Share of wealth (the total value of non-financial and financial assets (owned by the richest 1% of the population	Wealth Inequality

Annex 3. Complete List of components in the BridgeGap dataset

COMPONENT	DESCRIPTION
Corruption Perception	Country level assessment of the perceived levels of public sector corruption.
Single bidding	Assesses the prevalence and circumstances of contracts awarded through single-bid procurement processes, indicating the level of competition and transparency in public procurement.
Single Market Performance and Competitiveness	Measures how well the single market functions across member states, focusing on the enforcement of the four freedoms—goods, services, capital, and labour—and the competitiveness of the EU economy.
Public Integrity	Assesses of countries' capacity to prevent corruption by evaluating the balance between opportunities for corruption and the effectiveness of constraints—such as judicial independence, media freedom, and civil society engagement—used to hold power holders accountable and enforce public integrity.
Public accountability	Covers political and administrative accountability mechanisms.
Political Financing Regulation	Encompasses the assessment of the regulations, transparency, and enforcement mechanisms governing political financing
Financial Disclosure Regulation	Assesses the financial disclosure requirements for public officials to detect conflicts of interest, prevent illicit enrichment, and ensure transparency in their financial activities, helping to curb corruption and maintain accountability in public office.
Conflict of Interest Regulation	Assesses the policies and restrictions aimed at preventing conflicts of interest among public officials
Freedom of Information Regulation	Assesses the legal framework and implementation of freedom of information laws, focusing on access to government-held information, proactive disclosure, and mechanisms for ensuring accountability and transparency.
Public Procurement Regulation	Assesses the transparency, fairness, and regulatory compliance of public procurement processes, focusing on the availability of information, competition, and oversight mechanisms throughout key phases of procurement.
Criminal Law	Focuses on the criminal justice system's role in enforcing anti-corruption measures.
Fiscal Transparency	Assesses how openly governments disclose their budgeting processes, expenditures, and fiscal policies.
Administrative Transparency	Focuses on how government agencies and public institutions communicate their operations and decision-making processes. It measures the extent to which citizens can access crucial administrative data, such as policies, regulations, and the criteria for decision-making, which ensures that government actions are visible and accountable.
Judicial Transparency	This sub-component assesses the availability of court proceedings and legal decisions to the public, ensuring that the judiciary operates in an open manner. It also involves the publication of court rulings and legal interpretations.
Electoral Transparency	This sub-component assesses how well countries disclose information about their electoral processes, including voter registration, political campaign financing, and the integrity of the electoral outcomes
Political Transparency	This sub-component measures the availability and accessibility of key disclosures essential for promoting accountability in public office
Government Transparency	Assessing the legislative framework as well as factual conditions for g Government transparency

E-Services	Examines the availability and quality of online government services.
Enlightened Citizens	Assesses citizens' ability to engage with public services and governance digitally.
Judicial Independence	Evaluates the extent to which the judiciary operates free from external pressures or interference from the government, businesses, or other entities, ensuring impartial decision-making and rule of law.
Press Freedom	Measures the ability of the media to operate independently without censorship or political influence, assessing the role of free and independent journalism in holding power to account and promoting transparency.
International Enforcement	Covers countries' efforts to enforce international anti-corruption agreements, such as combatting transnational bribery and adhering to global frameworks.
National Enforcement	Focuses on domestic enforcement of anti-corruption laws, including the prosecution of corruption cases and the effectiveness of national anti-corruption agencies.